

A NUMERICAL APPROACH FOR LOW ENERGY IMPACTS ON COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING FE EXPLICIT CODES

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SUMMARY

The paper applies a numerical technique based on cohesive laws to investigate the development of interlaminar damage in low energy impacts on carbon composite laminates. The approach is assessed considering fracture toughness characterisation tests, the results of preliminary impact tests and literature evidences.

Keywords: cohesive elements, interlaminar fracture, damage tolerance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to increase the efficiency of the airframes, carbon fibre composite materials have been employed, during the later years, to manufacture not only secondary structural components, but also aircraft primary structures. One of the main factor that penalizes the application of these materials, particularly within a damage tolerance design approach, is their poor resistance to impact damage [1,2]. Impact phenomena on the aircraft structure can occur either at very high levels of velocity, as in the case of ballistic projectile as well as at low velocity levels such as in case of impact of debris, during taking off and landing, or as a consequence of tool drops during fabrication and maintenance activities [3]. These events can be characterised not only by an extensive range of velocities, but also by a large typology of impacting objects, thus leading to a wide range of impact energy levels, and can cause a variety of damages. In particular, low energy impacts on composite laminates produce large internal damage in the form of delamination, matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding and limited fibre breakage. Such a kind of damage, mainly caused by the concentrated applied shear loads and by the consequent flexural deformation of the impacted structure [3], can be difficult to be visually identified, due to the limited development of permanent denting on the impacted face. Hence, a barely visible impact damage (BVID) represents the damage level to be considered in the design of a damage tolerant structure, because it could hide significant delamination and lead to a serious degradation of the compressive strength of composite laminates. According to a damage tolerance design philosophy, a severe reduction of compression strain to failure is currently applied to panels in primary aircraft structure, considering their post-impact strength. Such an approach introduces significant weight penalties and greatly reduces the gain of structural efficiency that can be achieved by the adoption of composites. In order to assist the experimental phases in the design of damage tolerant composite structures, and to allow a purposeful reduction

of time and costs associated with mechanical testing, this paper proposes a numerical approach based on cohesive laws to model the onset and the development of interlaminar damage in carbon composite laminates. Cohesive elements have been already applied in FE analyses to model interlaminar failure process in composites, considering pre-cracked specimens, debonding of stiffeners parts from composite structures as well as impacts on composite skins [4-6]. The paper presents the application of such approach within a peculiar modeling technique, particularly suitable to analyses carried out by means of explicit time integration schemes. The experimental data considered in the work are first presented and the numerical approach is then described and assessed considering conventional tests for interlaminar toughness characterization. The performed impact analyses are subsequently presented and correlated with experimental results taken from literature [1,2,7] and with the results of preliminary impact tests carried out on laminates with known in-plane properties and measured interlaminar toughness.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section first presents the experiments carried out to measure the interlaminar toughness of a fabric (FB) and an unidirectional (UD) pre-preg material. The UD pre-preg has been used to manufacture a laminate that has been subsequently impacted at a 20 J energy level. The experimental data derived from such activity will be employed as a benchmark to prove the effectiveness of the proposed numerical approach and will provide the characterisation of the interfaces included in the numerical model of the impact. A partial review of the results reported in literature for low energy impact tests on carbon composite will then be reported. Such data will allow describing the typical damage modes in low energy impact, from a qualitative as well as from a quantitative point of view. Finally, the experiments performed on laminates made of the previously characterised UD pre-preg will be presented.

2.1. Interlaminar fracture tests in mode I (DCB) and mode II (ENF)

The materials considered in the presented experimental activity are a unidirectional tape IM7/8552 (UD) and fabric cloth AS4/8552 (FB). Three experimental tests have been performed with double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens and with end notched fracture (ENF) specimens to identify interlaminar toughness in mode I and II, respectively. Specimens with a length (L) of 200 mm and a width (b) of 25 mm have been used. A $[0]_{32}$ and $[0]_{24}$ lay-up have been chosen for the UD and fabric specimens, respectively, corresponding to a cured thickness of 4.0 mm and 6.7 mm. A pre-induced interlaminar crack has been obtained by interposing a PTFE sheet at the mid-plane of the laminates, for both the specimen types tested. Fig. 1-A presents the adopted lay-out for the DCB tests. As prescribed in [8], load is applied by means of two hinges, which have been connected to the specimens through 4 mm thick aluminium tabs bonded to the pre-cracked end (Fig. 1-B). Fig. 1-C presents a specimen during the test. The ENF experimental methodology is shown in Fig- 2-A. In order to obtain an unstable propagation of the pre induced fracture, the initial crack length has been set in the range $a/L < 1/\sqrt[3]{3} \approx 0.69$ [9]. Pre-opening phases have been performed for all the DCB and ENF tests in order to obtain a realistic fracture tip. Table 1 summarizes the test results and provides the values of G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} for both the pre-preg materials considered. The reported values of G_{Ic} represent an average between the toughness estimated by means of two data reduction methods (Modified Beam Theory and Compliance Calibration

Method) suggested by the ASTM standard [8]. The critical energy release rate in mode II (G_{IIc}) has been conveniently evaluated by applying a data reduction technique, derived from a classical beam theory analysis [9].

Fig. 1 – (A) Lay-out of the interlaminar fracture test in mode I; (B) Preparation of the specimens for the mode I test; (C) Test specimen during DCB test.

Fig. 2 – (A) Lay-out of the interlaminar fracture test in mode II; (B) FB specimen during ENF test.

Tab. 1 – Fracture toughness in mode I and mode II of the tested interlaminar layers.

	DCB Test (G_{Ic})	St. Dev. (G_{Ic})	ENF Test (G_{IIc})	St. Dev. (G_{IIc})
Fabric (AS4/8552)	1064 J/m ²	47 J/m ²	1750 J/m ²	320 J/m ²
UD (IM7/8552)	344 J/m ²	30 J/m ²	583 J/m ²	48 J/m ²

2.2. Low energy impact results from literature

Numerous studies have been performed in the past to investigate the parameters that influence the impact performance of a composite structure. Some of these are related to the configuration of the impacted laminate, such as lay-up sequence, elastic characteristic of the material constituents (fibre and resin), laminate thickness and structural shape, while others are related to the impacting object, such as its mass, shape and velocity [10]. All the studies agree to identify impact energy as the most significant parameter which determines the delamination area [1,2,7,11]. Fig. 3 shows the relationship between impact energy and delamination area for some tests presented in literature [1,2,7], performed on composite laminates with a quasi-isotropic lay-up sequence. All the data sets reported in Fig. 3 show a linear relation between impact energy level and the size of projected delamination area. The toughness in mode II drives the dimension of the interlaminar damage as shown by the comparison of the trends, shown in Fig. 3, referred to laminates containing HTA fibres with different resin systems: Excel 920 ($G_{IIc} \cong 730$ J/m² [1]) and Excel 922 ($G_{IIc} \cong 300$ J/m² [1]). The comparison shows that high levels of toughness in mode II lead to a reduction of the interlaminar damage area, thus increasing the impact resistance of the laminates [1]. Figure 3 also allows comparing composites with the same resin (Excel 922) and different fibre types, IMS and HTA. The comparison seems to suggest that low levels of fibre stiffness and strength (HTA) lead to decrease the interlaminar damage area for the

highest considered impact energy levels. Such behaviour can be explained by the fibre breakage which can provide an alternative energy absorption mechanism than delamination [1]. Such difference between the two considered composite materials is evident only for impact energy levels higher than 15 J, whereas for energy levels lower than 10 J the two materials behave similarly, due to the absence of fibre breakage.

Fig. 3 – Delamination Area vs. Impact Energy for different composite laminates [1,2,7].

Fig. 4 – (A) Drop weight test configuration; (B) C-scan detection on specimens with a non-conventional stacking sequence (IM7/8552) impacted at 20 J (dimension in mm).

2.3. Experimental results of 20 J impact tests on an IM7/8552 UD laminate

A series of impact tests has been performed at an energy level of 20 J following the procedure proposed by the ASTM standard [12] on a laminate made of IM7/8552 prepreg, previously characterized by means of DCB and ENF tests. An impactor with a diameter of 16 mm and a mass of 3.5 kg has been chosen. Tested specimens are 100 mm x 150 mm composite laminates with a non-conventional asymmetric stacking sequence of 32 plies and have a thickness of about 4 mm. Sequence presents 12.5% of plies at 0°, 75% at $\pm 45^\circ$ and the remaining 12.5% at 90°. Each specimen has been supported by a fixture base made of wood, shown in Fig. 4-A, and has been constrained by means of four clamps with rubber tips. An aluminium plate has been manually

interposed between the specimen and the impactor after the first rebound in order to avoid multiple impacts on the specimen. Six specimens were impacted and subjected to ultrasonic C-scan imaging. The six C-scan images, shown in Fig. 4-B, exhibit a typical roughly circular delamination area. Damage morphology agrees with the typical damage pattern of thick composite laminates impacted at low energy level, which is often referred to as pine tree [3]. The projected delaminated area measured from all the specimens tested provide an average value of about 1400 mm², which is in agreement with the experimental results reported in literature and shown in Fig. 3.

3. A NUMERICAL APPROACH TO MODEL INTERLAMINAR DAMAGE

The numerical methodology proposed in this paper to model the experiments described in section 2 derives from the approaches based on interface elements, which consider the composite laminate as an assembly of laminae connected by interfaces. The fracture processes occurring at the interfaces are described by using, as kinematic variables, the displacement discontinuities at an arbitrary material point belonging to an interface surface. Elements are characterised by traction-displacement laws that link the stress transmitted through the interface, σ , to the displacement discontinuities between the adjacent surfaces, δ (Fig. 5-A). Within this scheme, a zero-thickness interface element, endowed with a properly formulated continuum damage mechanics approach, can be used to model interlaminar damage. A basic requirement for such connection elements is to avoid relative displacements between the connected degrees of freedom before the onset of delamination. As the elements actually represent zero-thickness interfaces or layers with infinitesimal thickness, a very high stiffness is required to model the connection. Excessively compliant cohesive elements may significantly influence the model response and lead to unrealistic behaviour, but excessive stiffness may cause severe numerical problems and particularly spurious oscillations of the stress components [13].

Fig. 5 – (A) Description of interlaminar fracture in the interface and (B) in the proposed approach; (C) bi-linear response of interlaminar layers.

Several authors have suggested different methods to address such problems and to calibrate the penalty stiffness attributed to cohesive element basing on numerical as well as on physical considerations [13-15]. Further complications arise if an explicit time integration scheme is chosen for the computation. Such approach is typically employed to model high velocity transients but it implies the adoption of a conditionally stable integration time step, inversely proportional to the stiffness of the elements in the finite element scheme [16]. In view of that the extremely stiff connections introduced by cohesive elements may easily lead to unacceptable computational times. Such issues motivated the development of an alternative approach that considers a composite

laminate as an assembly of sublaminates, modeled by means of bi-dimensional elements. The kinematic variables used to describe the fracture process in mode I, II and III are the relative displacements at the mid-planes of such sublaminates (Fig. 5-B). The components of the relative displacement vector, Δ , can be associated to the three possible modes of fracture openings, as indicated in Eq. 1.

$$\Delta_I = \begin{cases} \Delta_z & \text{if } \Delta_z > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \Delta_z \leq 0 \end{cases}; \Delta_{II} = \Delta_x; \Delta_{III} = \Delta_y \quad (1)$$

Within a small strain assumption, the vector Δ can also be related to the average value of the out-of-plane strain components acting in the material volume between the sublaminates with thickness t_k (Eq. 2).

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \left\{ \varepsilon_{zz} \quad \gamma_{xz} \quad \gamma_{yz} \right\}^T = \Delta / t_k \quad (2)$$

A linear 8-noded solid element with a reduced integration scheme can be adopted as connection element, so that the out-of-plane strain components at its single integration point match the average strain state represented in Eq. 2 [16]. Such element is customarily adopted in explicit finite element computations, which represent the main field of application for the proposed approach. Accordingly, it represents an adequate choice for the connection element, provided that only the out-of-plane response is included in its constitutive behaviour. The response of the connection element can be modelled as in Eq. 3, where a scalar damage variable has been introduced to model the fracture process.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_{zz} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & G_{xz} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{yz} \end{bmatrix} (1-d) \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{zz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The resulting finite element scheme, made of bi-dimensional elements which represents the composite plies connected by solid elements with null in-plane response, guarantees the translational equilibrium of a ply included in a laminate lay-up. Considering a bended laminate, as the one sketched in Fig. 6-A, the translational equilibrium of a single ply can be formalised as in Eq. 4, where N is the membrane force per unit width and τ is the shear stress transferred through the interfaces.

$$\frac{dN_{xx}}{dx} = \tau_{xz}(z+dz) - \tau_{xz}(z) \quad (4)$$

In the proposed modelling technique the area of the ply cross section is considered lumped at the ply mid-plane and it is represented by a bi-dimensional element, such as a membrane or a shell element. Considering the constant stress elements typically adopted in explicit finite element schemes, Fig. 6-B indicates how solid elements with null in-plane response and bi-dimensional element can satisfy the equilibrium of a node in the finite element model, fulfilling Eq. 4. The capability of the technique to model the bending response of composite laminates has been assessed by several numerical benchmarks and correlation with experimental tests reported in [6].

Fig. 6 – Stress resultants acting on a single lamina in bending conditions (A) and proposed finite element scheme (B).

The onset and the evolution of the damage variable introduced in Eq. 3 can be set to model the strength and the toughness of the interlaminar layers. To accomplish such objective, the approaches based on the interface elements typically exploit the links between the critical energy release rates and the energy dissipated in the damage process [4]. The same procedure can be followed in the proposed approach. Taking into consideration Eq. 2, the link between the strain-stress response and the energy release rates for fractures opening in mode I and II can be expressed as in Eq. 5.

$$\int_0^{\infty} \sigma_{zz} d\Delta_I = t_k \int_0^{\infty} \sigma_{zz} d\varepsilon_{zz} = G_{Ic} \quad ; \quad \int_0^{\infty} \tau_{xz} d\Delta_{II} = t_k \int_0^{\infty} \tau_{xz} d\gamma_{zx} = G_{IIc} \quad (5)$$

Equations 2 and 5 allow converting a generic traction-displacement law in a stress-strain response attributed to the solid elements. Throughout this work, the cohesive law described in [4] has been adopted, converted into a stress-strain model and implemented in a FORTRAN VUMAT subroutine to be linked to the Abaqus Explicit Code. The law is based on the bi-linear response, shown in Fig. 5-C. Properties in mode II and mode III are considered identical. Damage onset in processes evolving in pure mode I or mode II occurs beyond the peak stress σ_{I0} and σ_{II0} , which represent the axial and shear strength of the interlaminar layer. Mixed mode processes are addressed by introducing a strength criterion and a toughness criterion, as described by several authors [4,17].

4. NUMERICAL ANALYSES

4.1. Numerical-Experimental correlation of DCB and ENF tests

FE models of the experimental DCB tests have been developed both for IM7/8552 (UD) as well as for AS4/8552 (FB) pre-preg materials. A mesh grid with 1.25 mm x 1.25 mm in-plane dimensions has been chosen, in agreement with indications provided in [13]. Shell elements (*S4R* [16]) have been adopted to model sublaminates consisting of two plies, connected by solid elements (*C3D8R* [16]) endowed with the material law described in section 3. Such choice lead to model 15 and 11 layers of connection elements in the models of the UD and of the fabric DCB specimens, respectively. Shell elements have been characterized by a purely elastic orthotropic material model with the in-plane elastic properties reported in Tab. 2. Solid elements between shells have been characterized by the physical out-of-plane moduli of the material, also reported in Tab. 2, and by the toughness reported in Tab. 1. Interlaminar strengths σ_{I0} and σ_{II0} have been identified, for the UD material, after a sensitivity study carried out on the model of low energy impacts, which will be reported in the following par. 4.2. The same values have been adopted for the fabric materials. The pre-induced crack has been modeled by

attributing an initial damage condition to the mid-plane interlaminar layer so to reproduce the crack length after the pre-opening phase of the test. The explicit FE analyses have been performed with a velocity boundary condition applied to the loading tip. The adopted velocity time history allowed avoiding the onset of dynamic oscillation during the loading phase. Fig. 7-A presents the interlaminar damage evolution in mode I for the DCB test on the fabric specimen, whereas Fig. 7-B reports the numerical-experimental correlation in terms of load displacement curve, for both the composite materials considered. The correlation obtained for the fabric is very good either for the linear response until the onset of crack propagation, as well as for the prediction of residual load carrying capability of the specimen. Discrepancies can be observed in the loading phase of the correlation of the UD test, where the numerical model tends to overestimate the global stiffness of the specimens. The numerical approach confirms its capability to follow the load carrying capability of the sample during the stable propagation of a crack.

Tab. 2 – In-plane and interlaminar elastic properties of considered pre-preg.

	AS4/8552	IM7/8552		AS4/8552	IM7/8552
E_{11}	61 GPa	155 GPa	E_{33}	7.8 GPa	7.8 GPa
E_{22}	61 GPa	10 GPa	$G_{13} = G_{23}$	3 GPa	3 GPa
G_{12}	4.4 GPa	4.5 GPa	σ_{I0}	35 MPa	35 MPa
ν_{12}	0.05	0.3	σ_{II0}	70 MPa	70 MPa

Fig. 7 – (A) Evolution of interlaminar damage in mode I; (B) Load vs Displacements for numerical-experimental correlation of DCB UD and FB.

The same finite element schemes developed for the DCB tests have been employed in the ENF analysis. A similar technique has also been used to model the pre-crack. Rigid cylindrical surfaces have been analytically defined in order to model the load application rollers, interacting by means of penalty contact algorithms with the specimen surfaces. The central cylinder was moved downward using an appropriate velocity law in order to avoid high frequency mode excitation. Fig. 8-A reports the contour of interlaminar damage, after the unstable propagation of the crack, obtained in the analysis of an ENF FB test, whereas Fig. 8-B presents the overall numerical-experimental correlation. Although the numerical response of the ENF FB model seems to underestimate the stiffness exhibited by the specimen during the test, the analyses correctly identify the onset of unstable crack propagation for both the considered

materials. Globally, ENF analyses indicate that the numerical approach is capable to correctly predict the load level at the onset of an unstable crack propagation and to model such propagation regime. It should be pointed out that models have overestimated in both cases the propagation length of the crack after the phase of unstable propagation. Such tendency is in agreement with the observation reported in [6], referred to quasi-static analyses.

Fig. 8 – (A) Evolution of the interlaminar damage in mode II; (B) Load vs Displacements for numerical-experimental correlation of ENF UD and FB.

4.2. Numerical analyses of standard impact test configuration at 8 J

A numerical analysis of an 8 J impact has been performed following the test lay-out suggested by the reference ASTM standard [12]. The developed model represents a laminate made of 32 IM7/8552 unidirectional plies with a quasi-isotropic lay-up sequence: $[45/0/-45/90]_{4S}$. After some preliminary numerical tests, it has been decided to separately model each ply of the composite laminate. Hence, the final model includes 32 shell (*S4R* [16]) layers connected by 31 solid elements. The in-plane typical length of the adopted finite element scheme in the contact zone has been set to 1 mm. The impactor has been modeled as a deformable body with a mass of 1.58 kg, made of steel with a 16 mm diameter semi-spherical end [12]. An initial velocity condition along the vertical direction, has been attributed to the impactor.

Fig. 9 – (A) Interlaminar damage; (B) Force history of a 8 J impact on IM7/8552.

Fig. 9-A reports the contour of the interlaminar damage during the impact analysis. The values of interlaminar strengths, σ_{I0} and σ_{II0} , have been initially set to relatively low levels (25 MPa and 50 MPa, respectively) and have been subsequently increased to the values reported in Tab. 2. Such choice lead to a numerical prediction of the projected delamination area of about 880 mm², which is in good agreement with the experimental results reported in Fig. 3.

4.3. Numerical analyses of 20 J impacts

The modelling technique has been also applied to model an impact at an energy level of 20 J on the same laminate considered for the impact at 8 J. After some preliminary tests, numerical problems lead to reduce at 0.5 mm the typical in-plane size of the elements in the zone under the impactor. The same impactor model has been used and the material models of the laminate have been calibrated identically to the previously described impact case. Figure 10-A shows the contour of interlaminar damage at the end of the analysis. A damage pattern characterised by a pine tree shape has been obtained. It can be observed that one interlaminar layer, approximately at the mid-plane of the laminate, presents an extensive delamination, which deviates from the pine tree pattern. Damage extent in such interlaminar layer leads to evaluate a numerical delaminated area of 3800 mm², which noticeably exceeds the experimental results reported in Fig. 3 for the corresponding impact energy level. This result could be attributed to the tendency of overestimating the length of the cracks that propagate in unstable regime, already pointed out in par. 4.1. If such interlaminar layer is not considered in the evaluation of delaminated area, a value of 1300 mm² is obtained, which is well within the range of the data reported in Fig. 3. Figure 10-B reports the results obtained considering the non-conventional asymmetric lay-up sequence adopted in the test described in par. 2.3. The occurrence of a large delamination in a single interlaminar layer can also be observed in Fig. 10-B, although the change of lay-up affected the numerical results and a pine tree shape can not be clearly recognized in the damage pattern. The extent of delaminated area turns out to be of 3400 mm² considering the most damaged interlaminar layer, but it is reduced to 1650 mm² if such layer is ignored. The latter result is in acceptable agreement with the experimental level of 1400 mm² evaluated by the C-Scan images reported in Fig. 4.

Fig. 10 Interlaminar damage in the analyses of 20 J impact on (A) a quasi-isotropic laminate and (B) on a non-conventional asymmetric laminate.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A numerical approach based on cohesive laws to model interlaminar damage propagation in composite laminate during characterisation tests and low energy impacts

has been presented. The approach adopts a constitutive model presented in literature, adapted to a peculiar modelling technique, which is suitable to be employed in explicit finite element computations. Such technique allowed modelling several and possibly all the interlaminar layers of a laminate. Good results have been obtained considering stable crack propagation in DCB tests and unstable crack propagations in ENF tests for two different pre-preg materials, although ENF test analyses indicated the tendency of the model to overestimate the length of cracks propagating in unstable mode. The approach has been subsequently applied to model low energy impact in 4 mm thick composite specimens, consisting of 32 plies which have all been separately modelled. The results obtained in terms of damage patterns and delaminated area can be considered promising, as they turn out to be in agreement with the data reported in literature if single interlaminar layers, characterised by an atypical development of damage, are ignored. Such overestimation could also be related to the absence of dissipation mechanics alternative than delamination, as in plane matrix damage or fibre breakage, which could play a significant role at the considered impact energy levels and should be included in the model to completely address the physical aspects of the phenomena.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cartié D.D.R., Irving P.E., Effect of resin and fibre properties on impact and compression after impact performance of CFRP. *Composites: Part A* 2002; 33: 483-93.
- [2] Zhang X., Hounslow L., Grassi M. Improvement of low-velocity impact and compression-after-impact performance by z-fibre pinning. *Composite Science and Technology* 2006; 66: 2785-94.
- [3] Abrate S. *Impact on composite structures*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998.
- [4] Davila CG. Mixed mode decohesion elements for analyses of progressive delaminations. 42nd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Material Conference and Exhibit, Seattle, WA, USA, April 16-19, 2001.
- [5] Johnson A, Holzpappel M. Modeling of soft body impact on a composite structure. *Comp Struct* 2003;61:103-113.
- [6] Airoidi A., Bettini P. Sala G., Evaluation of numerical approaches for the development of interlaminar damage in composite laminates, 16th International Conference on Composite Materials, Kyoto, Japan, July 8-13, 2007.
- [7] Papanicolaou, G.C. and Stavropoulos, C.D. (1995). New approach for residual compressive strength prediction of impacted CFRP laminates. *Composites* 1995; 26(7): 517-23.
- [8] ASTM D 5528. Standard Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite.
- [9] Carlsson, L, Gillespie JW, Mode-II interlaminar fracture of composites, in "Application of the fracture mechanics to composite materials". Editor Friedrich, K. Composite Material Series No. 6. Elsevier Science Publishers BV 1989.
- [10] Federal Aviation Administration (1998). Enhanced Reliability Prediction Methodology for Impact Damaged Composite Structures – Final Report. Virginia: National Technical Information Service.

- [11] Sala G. Impact behaviour of heat-resistant toughened composites. *Composites Part B* 2000; 31: 161-73.
- [12] ASTM International (2005a). D7136 – Standard test method for measuring the damage resistance of a fibre reinforced polymer matrix composite to a drop weight impact event. *Annual Book of ASTM Standards* 2005: 430-445.
- [13] Turon A, Davila CG, Camanho PP, Costa J, An engineering solution for mesh size effect in the simulation of delamination using cohesive zone models. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 2007; 74:1665-1682.
- [14] Daudeville L, Allix O, Ladeveze P. Delamination analysis by damage mechanics. Some applications. *Compos Engng* 1995;5(1):17–24.
- [15] Zou Z, Reid SR, Li S, Soden PD. Modelling interlaminar and intralaminar damage in filament wound pipes under quasi-static indentation. *J Compos Mater* 2002;36:477–99.
- [16] Abaqus®. Theory and User's Manuals. Hibbit, Karlsson & Sorensen. Pawtucket, USA, 2004.
- [17] Hu N., Zemba Y., Okabe T., Yan C., Fukunaga H., Elamarkbi A.M., A new cohesive model for simulating delamination propagation in composite laminates under transverse loads, *Mechanics of Materials* 40 (2008) pp. 920-935.